

CREATIVE PEOPLE AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF SUPERIOR CAPTURE FISHERY PRODUCTS IN SAMOTA

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the role of creative individuals in the development of superior captured fish products in Teluk Santong Village, SAMOTA area, Sumbawa Regency. Human resource creativity is an important factor in increasing the added value of fishery products through product innovation and business management. This associative study involved 97 respondents consisting of fishermen who had participated in product development training activities. Data were collected through questionnaires and processed using Smart Partial Least Square (SmartPLS) software to test the relationship between variables. Creative individuals were the independent variable, while the dependent variable was the development of superior products, with training as a medium for capacity building. The results showed that the creativity of capture fishermen had a positive and significant influence on the development of superior products through training. This means that the higher the level of creativity possessed by fishermen, especially after participating in training, the greater their ability to develop products based on captured fish with higher economic value and competitiveness. This finding confirms that the development of creative individuals is a key factor in driving local economic transformation based on marine and fisheries potential. Therefore, the sustainability of creativity-based training and mentoring programs needs to be strengthened to encourage the creation of sustainable superior product innovation in the SAMOTA area.

Keywords: Creative People, Training, Superior Products, Catching Fish, SAMOTA

INTRODUCTION

The capture fisheries sector is a significant contributor to the economy of Indonesia's coastal communities, both in terms of food availability, employment, and contribution to regional income (Suhartono et al., 2022; FAO, 2022; Hilborn et al., 2020; Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, 2023). In Indonesia, capture fisheries play a strategic role in supporting the blue economy and sustainable development of coastal areas (Béné et al., 2021; Bailey et al., 2021). Despite the abundant potential of marine products, particularly in the SAMOTA area (Saleh Bay, Moyo Island, Mount Tambora) of Sumbawa Regency, most capture fisheries products are still marketed as fresh or raw fish (Fitriani & Hamzah, 2021). This results in relatively low economic added value for fishermen and their vulnerability to market price dynamics (Asche et al., 2022; Bush & Oosterveer, 2020). Increasing product added value depends not only on the availability of natural resources but also on the ability of human resources to process, develop, and market valuable products (Barney, 1991; Teece, 2018). Within the framework of human capital development, training and education are seen as investments that improve the skills and competencies of entrepreneurs, thereby driving productivity and innovation (Putra & Rahayu, 2023; Becker, 1993; Wright & McMahan, 2011). Creativity is a crucial asset in the innovation process because it enables entrepreneurs to generate new ideas, modify products, and create differentiation that can meet market needs (Nasution et al., 2021; Gherhes et al., 2020; Ismail et al., 2022; Prasetyo & Kistanti, 2022). Amidst global economic dynamics, the concept of the creative economy increasingly positions product innovation as key to the competitiveness of small and medium enterprises (Wahyuni & Purnomo, 2020; Amabile & Pratt, 2016; Anderson et al., 2014). In the context of capture fisheries, product innovation and diversification are important strategies for expanding markets and increasing fishermen's incomes (Susanto et al., 2024; Haryanto, 2022). The resource-based perspective emphasizes that a business's competitive advantage depends on unique and difficult-to-imitate resources, including the knowledge, expertise, and creativity of entrepreneurs (Kusdiantoro et al., 2020; Susanto et al., 2024; Tidd & Bessant, 2021).

Training plays a crucial role in developing the technical and non-technical skills of business actors. Training can strengthen competencies, entrepreneurial attitudes, and innovation skills, ultimately boosting business performance (Prasetyo & Kistanti, 2022). In the fisheries sector, technical training in product processing, sanitation, product packaging, and digital marketing are critical elements with the potential to transform traditional production patterns into more competitive and value-added businesses. Although various studies have explored the relationship between training and business performance, as well as between innovation and product competitiveness, comprehensive studies examining the relationship between creativity, training, and superior product development in the context of coastal community capture fisheries are still relatively limited, particularly in the SAMOTA region (Kusdiantoro et al., 2020). Most studies focus more on technical aspects of production, supply chain management, or technology adoption, without detailing the mechanisms by which training can strengthen the relationship between creativity and superior product development.

This gap underpins the importance of this research. A deeper understanding of the role of creativity and training in fostering the development of superior products in the fisheries sector not only provides conceptual contributions to the study of the creative economy and strengthening human resource capacity, but also forms the basis for policy recommendations to strengthen the capacity of fishermen to increase the added value of their products (Fauzi & Anna, 2023). Based on this description, this study aims to analyze the role of human creativity in the development of superior products from fishing in Teluk Santong Village, SAMOTA area, Sumbawa Regency, with training as a strengthening variable. The results of this study are expected to demonstrate that fishing creativity has a positive and significant influence on the development of superior products through training.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Product Development

Superior product development is the process of creating, refining, or diversifying products that are unique, high in quality, and competitive compared to similar products. In the capture fisheries sector, superior products are measured not only by the quantity of catch but also by the added value generated through processing, innovation, and product differentiation (Tidd & Bessant, 2021). Superior products can be realized through improving the quality of raw materials, innovating recipes or product variants, improving packaging, quality certification, and implementing effective marketing strategies. Superior product development aims to increase the economic value of catches while expanding market access, both locally and regionally (Asche et al., 2022; Béné et al., 2021). Within the framework of local economic development, superior products are a crucial instrument for driving income growth in coastal communities. Products with higher added value and uniqueness tend to have larger profit margins and are more resilient to fluctuations in raw commodity prices (Bailey et al., 2021; KKP, 2023). Conceptually, the development of superior products is influenced by an individual's ability to innovate and utilize knowledge gained through training. Creativity provides the initial idea, while training provides the technical implementation tools that enable the idea to be translated into a tangible product. Therefore, the combination of human creativity and training is believed to be a crucial factor in driving the development of superior catch-based products in the SAMOTA region.

Human Creativity

Human creativity is an individual's ability to generate new ideas, alternative solutions, or combinations of ideas that have utility and relevance to specific problems (Amabile & Pratt, 2016). In the context of a local resource-based economy, creativity is not only defined as artistic ability but also as the capacity for innovative thinking in transforming available potential into products with added economic value (Anderson et al., 2014; Tidd & Bessant, 2021). In the small business sector and coastal communities, creativity is a key factor in creating product differentiation. Fishermen with high levels of creativity tend to be more adaptive to market changes, more open to learning, and able to develop product variations based on their catch. Creativity also encourages diversification ideas, such as processing fish into processed products, packaging innovations, and more attractive marketing strategies. Conceptually, creativity is a component of human capital that can be enhanced through learning and experience. Creative individuals generally possess a strong sense of curiosity, the courage to try new things, and the ability to solve problems flexibly (Gherhes et al., 2020; Dewi & Yasa, 2022). In the context of training, individuals with high levels of creativity tend to more easily absorb material, apply new knowledge, and develop further innovations. Therefore, the higher the level of human creativity possessed by fishermen or capture fisheries entrepreneurs, the more likely they are to actively participate in training and utilize it to develop their business capacity. Based on this description, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H1: Human creativity has a positive and significant effect on training.

Training

Training is a systematic process designed to improve individual knowledge, skills, and attitudes in order to enhance performance and productivity. In the context of small business development, training serves not only as a transfer of technical knowledge but also as a means of fostering an entrepreneurial and innovative mindset. In the capture fisheries sector, training can cover various aspects, such as fishery processing techniques, sanitation and hygiene standards, product packaging, business management, and digital-based marketing (Ismail et al., 2022; FAO, 2022). Through training, fishermen gain new insights that enable them to transform traditional production patterns into more modern, market-oriented businesses. Training also acts as a bridge between individual creativity and the practical implementation of innovation. Individuals' creative ideas often cannot be optimally realized without adequate technical and managerial skills (Wright & McMahan, 2011). Therefore, training serves to strengthen individuals' capacity to translate creative ideas into products with economic value. Empirically, improving the quality of relevant and sustainable training has the potential to enhance entrepreneurs' ability to create competitive, superior products (Prasetyo & Kistanti, 2022). Effective training will improve production competency, product quality, and adaptability to market needs. Based on this description, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H2: Training has a positive and significant effect on the development of superior products.

Research Framework

The following is the framework of this research.

Figure 1. Framework of Thought

This research framework is based on the premise that the development of superior products in the capture fisheries sector in the SAMOTA region is determined not only by the availability of natural resources but also by the quality and capacity of the human resources who manage them. In this model, human creativity is positioned as an exogenous variable reflecting the ability of fishermen to generate ideas, innovate, and modify captured products. However, this creative potential requires capacity building support through training to be effectively implemented in production and processing activities. Therefore, training acts as a reinforcing variable that bridges individual creativity with the ability to develop superior products. The development of superior products then becomes an endogenous variable representing the increased added value, quality, and competitiveness of captured fish-based products. Thus, this research framework emphasizes that the synergy between creativity and training is a crucial factor in driving the transformation of a more sustainable and competitive local fisheries-based economy.

METHOD

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative approach with an explanatory research design. This approach was chosen because the study aimed to explain the causal relationships between variables, namely human creativity, training, and superior product development in the capture fisheries sector. This study was cross-sectional, where data was collected over a specific time period to capture the actual conditions of respondents related to the variables studied.

Research Location and Subjects

The research was conducted in Teluk Santong Village, located in the SAMOTA area (Teluk Saleh, Moyo Island, and Mount Tambora), Sumbawa Regency. The location was selected based on the consideration that this area

has significant capture fisheries potential and has become part of a marine-based economic development strategy. The research subjects were fishermen and fishery product processing business actors involved in developing superior products based on catch results.

Population and Sampling Techniques

The population in this study were all fishermen and business actors involved in the development of superior products based on captured fish in Teluk Santong Village, Plampang District, Sumbawa Regency. The sample was determined using a purposive sampling technique, considering that the exact population size was unknown. This technique was chosen by establishing certain criteria so that the respondents involved were truly relevant to the research objectives. The respondent criteria included: (1) working as a capture fisherman, fishery product processor, or business actor in the capture fisheries sector; (2) domiciled in Teluk Santong Village; and (3) having participated in training activities related to fishery product development.

Data Types and Sources

This study uses quantitative data obtained through a structured questionnaire survey. Primary data was obtained directly from respondents by completing the research instrument. Meanwhile, secondary data was obtained from official local government documents, regional development reports, and relevant literature sources to support the conceptual analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research result

Validity Test, AVE, and Reliability Test

The following presents the results of the validity, reliability and AVE tests which have been summarized in the table below.

Table 1. Results of validity test, AVE, and reliability test

Variables and Indicators	Factor Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	AVE
Training		0.991	0.973
M.1.1	0.986		
M.1.2	0.986		
M.1.3	0.987		
M.1.4	0.986		
Human Creativity		0.998	0.994
X.1	0.995		
X.2	0.996		
X.3	0.996		
X.4	0.999		
X.5	0.998		
Development of Featured Products		0.988	0.945
Y.1	0.980		
Y.2	0.967		
Y.3	0.967		
Y.4	0.971		
Y.5	0.967		
Y.6	0.981		

The results of the measurement model evaluation (outer model) show that all indicators in the variables of Training, Human Creativity, and Superior Product Development have factor loadings values above 0.70, even in the very high range, namely between 0.967 to 0.999. This value indicates that each indicator has a very strong ability to reflect the latent construct being measured, so that the convergent validity criteria have been met. In addition, the Cronbach's Alpha value for each variable also shows a very high level of internal reliability, namely 0.991 for Training, 0.998 for Human Creativity, and 0.988 for Superior Product Development. These values far exceed the

minimum limit of 0.70, which means that all indicators in each construct have very good consistency in measuring the same concept. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values for each variable were recorded at 0.973 for Training, 0.994 for Human Creativity, and 0.945 for Superior Product Development. All AVE values were above the threshold of 0.50, indicating that most of the indicator variance can be explained by the measured latent constructs. Therefore, it can be concluded that the measurement model in this study has met the criteria for convergent validity and internal reliability very well. Overall, these results indicate that the model is suitable to proceed to the structural model evaluation stage (inner model).

R-Square Test

The following presents the results of the determination test which have been summarized in the table below.

Table 2. R-Square Value

Variables	R Square
Training	0.031
Development of superior products	0.089

This study used one dependent variable that was influenced by several independent variables. The results of the analysis showed that the R-Square (R²) value for the creativity in training variable was 0.031 or 3.1%, and the R-Square (R²) value for the superior product development variable was 0.089 or 8.9%. This indicates that the construct of human creativity has a 3.1% influence on creativity in training, while the variables of human creativity, creativity in training, and product innovation together are able to explain the development of superior products by 8.9%. Meanwhile, the remaining 91.1% is influenced by other factors outside this research model.

Hypothesis Testing

The following presents the results of the hypothesis test which have been summarized in the table below.

Table 3. Hypothesis Test Results

	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Training -> Superior Product Development	0.083	3,589	0.000	Accepted
Human Creativity -> Training	0.105	1,687	0.047	Accepted

DISCUSSION

Training influences the development of superior products

The test results show that the relationship between Training and Superior Product Development has a T-statistic value of 3.589 with a P-value of 0.000. T-statistic values greater than 1.96 and P-values far below 0.05 indicate that the effect is significant at the 95% confidence level. Thus, the first hypothesis stating that training has a positive effect on the development of superior products is declared accepted. Substantively, this finding indicates that the training attended by fishermen and capture fisheries business actors in Teluk Santong Village has a real contribution to improving the quality and added value of captured products. Training not only functions as a formal knowledge transfer activity, but also as a means of increasing technical and managerial capacity. Training materials that include fishery product processing techniques, hygiene and sanitation standards, recipe innovations and product variants, more attractive packaging techniques, and marketing strategies, directly encourage product diversification. Fishermen who previously sold their catch in the form of fresh fish are now able to develop processed products such as smoked fish, fish floss, or other processed-based products that have a longer shelf life and higher selling value.

Furthermore, the training also raised business owners' awareness of the importance of product quality and standards in facing market competition. Understanding more modern and informative packaging, labeling, and simple marketing strategies through social media helped expand market access for local fishery products. This demonstrates that the training acts as a catalyst in the transformation of traditional businesses into more market-oriented and value-added businesses. The strength of this influence is reflected in the relatively high T-statistic value compared to other relationships in the research model. This means that training is a factor that consistently and significantly influences the ability of business actors to develop superior products. In the context of the SAMOTA

region, which has abundant fishery resource potential, this finding confirms that optimizing this potential is highly dependent on capacity-building interventions through sustainable training programs relevant to the needs of coastal communities. In other words, training is a strategic instrument in encouraging increased competitiveness and sustainability of the local capture fisheries-based economy.

Human Creativity Influences Training

The test results show that the relationship between Human Creativity and Training has a T-statistic value of 1.687 with a P-value of 0.047. P-values smaller than 0.05 indicate that the effect is significant at the 95% confidence level, so the second hypothesis is declared accepted. However, the T-statistic value is slightly below the conventional threshold of 1.96 indicates that the level of significance of this relationship is marginal or relatively not very strong compared to the relationship in the first hypothesis. Substantively, these findings indicate that the level of creativity of fishermen and capture fisheries business actors influences the effectiveness of the training they attend. Individuals who have higher creativity tend to be more open to learning, more active in the training process, and more quickly understand and adapt the material provided. In the context of Teluk Santong Village, fishermen who have the ability to generate new ideas or the courage to try different processing methods show more intense participation in training activities and are better able to apply the material they have received.

Creativity also plays a role in maximizing the benefits of training. The same training material can have different impacts depending on an individual's capacity to process and implement it. Creative fishermen don't just passively receive information but are able to develop further ideas based on the material provided, such as creating new flavor variants, changing packaging designs to make them more attractive, or adapting products to local market tastes. Thus, creativity becomes an internal factor that supports the optimization of training programs. However, the relatively lower influence strength indicates that training effectiveness is not solely determined by individual creativity. Other factors such as the quality of the facilitator, the relevance of the material, the delivery method, local government support, and the availability of production facilities likely also play a significant role in determining training success. Therefore, although creativity has been shown to have a significant influence on training, this influence is supportive and not the sole determinant. This finding implies that strengthening the creativity of coastal communities remains important, but needs to be accompanied by training designs that are adaptive, applicable, and tailored to the real needs of capture fisheries business actors in the SAMOTA region.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that human creativity is a crucial factor in strengthening the capacity of capture fisheries business actors in the SAMOTA region, particularly in the development of superior products based on marine catches. Individual creativity has been shown to contribute to the effectiveness of training, which in turn plays a significant role in enhancing the capabilities of fishermen and business actors in product diversification, processing innovation, and improving product quality and competitiveness. Thus, training serves as a mediating variable that bridges internal potential (creativity) with external outcomes in the form of developing superior products with added economic value. These findings confirm that strengthening the capture fisheries sector requires more than just relying on natural resources; it also requires investment in human resources through structured, applicable, and sustainable training programs. Local governments and relevant stakeholders need to design training programs that are not only technical in nature but also encourage innovation, entrepreneurship, modern packaging, and digital-based marketing strategies. This approach is crucial for sustainably optimizing the marine economic potential in the SAMOTA region and improving the well-being of coastal communities. The results of this study pave the way for the development of a more comprehensive model in future research. It is recommended that future studies include additional variables such as government policy support, utilization of processing and marketing technology, and socio-economic networks that can strengthen the fisheries business ecosystem. The addition of these variables is expected to provide a more comprehensive picture of the factors influencing the development of superior products and increase the theoretical and practical exploratory power of the research model.

REFERENCES

- Alamsyah, DP, & Lestari, R. (2021). Entrepreneurship training and innovation capability of SMEs. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*, 24(3).
- Amabile, T. M., & Pratt, M. G. (2016). The dynamic componential model of creativity and innovation. *Research in Organizational Behavior*, 36, 157–183.

- Anderson, N., Potočník, K., & Zhou, J. (2014). Innovation and creativity in organizations. *Journal of Management*, 40(5), 1297–1333.
- Arifin, B., et al. (2021). Coastal development and fisheries sustainability in Indonesia. *Marine Policy*, 132, 104669.
- Asche, F., et al. (2022). Seafood value chains and sustainability. *Marine Policy*, 138, 104984.
- Bailey, M., et al. (2021). Small-scale fisheries and economic resilience. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 203, 105523.
- Barney, J. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of Management*, 17(1), 99–120.
- Becker, G. (1993). *Human Capital*. University of Chicago Press.
- Béné, C., et al. (2021). Small-scale fisheries and sustainable development. *World Development*, 144, 105473.
- Bush, S. R., & Oosterveer, P. (2020). Governing sustainable seafood. *Marine Policy*, 117, 103925.
- Dewi, NLPR, & Yasa, INM (2022). Creativity and SME performance. *Journal of Business Management*, 19(3), 301–315.
- F.A.O. (2022). *The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2022*. Rome.
- Fauzi, A., & Anna, Z. (2023). Fisheries sustainability and local economy. *Marine Policy*, 148, 105379.
- Fitriani, D., & Hamzah, A. (2021). Value added of fishery products. *Journal of Marine and Fisheries Socioeconomics*, 16(1), 45–56.
- Gherhes, C., et al. (2020). Entrepreneurship education and innovation. *Education + Training*, 62(2), 173–192.
- Haryanto, T. (2022). Resource-based view in SMEs. *Journal of Management and Entrepreneurship*, 24(3), 233–245.
- Hilborn, R., et al. (2020). Effective fisheries management. *PNAS*, 117(4), 2218–2224.
- Ismail, D., et al. (2022). Training impact on SMEs performance. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 60(4), 789–812.
- Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries. (2023). *2023 Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Performance Report*.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2021). *Marketing Management* (16th ed.). Pearson.
- Kusdiantoro, K., et al. (2020). Sustainable capture fisheries strategy. *Marine Fisheries*, 11(2), 123–134.
- Lestari, E., & Handayani, S. (2023). Training and SME capacity building. *Journal of Socioeconomics*, 18(1), 55–68.
- Mulyadi, D., & Setiawan, R. (2021). Training effectiveness on SME performance. *Journal of Business Administration*, 10(2).
- Nasution, AH, et al. (2021). Creativity and innovation in SMEs. *International Journal of Innovation Management*, 25(6).
- Noe, R. A. (2020). *Employee Training and Development*. McGraw-Hill.
- OECD. (2021). *Skills for Economic Recovery*. Paris.
- Prasetyo, PE, & Kistanti, NR (2022). Training and SME performance. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 25(2), 157–170.
- Rahmawati, T., & Sari, DP (2022). Regional flagship products. *Journal of Development Planning*, 6(2).
- Runco, M. A., & Jaeger, G. J. (2020). The standard definition of creativity. *Creativity Research Journal*, 32(1).
- Sari, M., & Widodo, T. (2024). Human capital in coastal economy. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 246, 106890.
- Suhartono, S., et al. (2022). Fisheries sector contribution. *Journal of Fisheries Science*, 14(2).
- Susanto, H., et al. (2024). Diversification of fishery products. *Indonesian Agribusiness Journal*, 12(1), 41–54.
- Teece, D. (2018). Dynamic capabilities. *Long Range Planning*, 51(1), 40–58.
- Tidd, J., & Bessant, J. (2021). *Managing Innovation*. Wiley.
- UNCTAD. (2022). *Creative Economy Outlook 2022*.
- UNESCO. (2022). *Creative Economy Outlook*.
- Utami, NW, & Prabowo, H. (2021). Innovation in fishing SMEs. *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*, 33(4).
- Wahyuni, S., & Purnomo, EP (2020). Creative economic development. *Journal of Indonesian Economy*, 5(2).